

DESIGN AS A PROPOSED EXPERIENCE: A NEW CONCEPT OF WELL LIVING

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to analyze the synergy of experience design, housing and social responsibility in the development of regionalization in Brazil. By promoting new experiments of living and design, developers focus not only on the welfare and convenience of communities, but mainly in privacy, security and sustainable development, all of which have social and political impacts. Such analysis are identified based on the concepts of authors such as Bauman, Hill, McLellan, Celaschi, Fluser among others and intended at contributing to the fields of design, communication and regionalization development.

Keywords: laddering research, experience design, territory design, consumer behavior, service.

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary society presents itself as a space nearly endless for studies and academic research. Permeated by a plurality in its most varied aspects, the human living space alone motivates researchers from all fields of knowledge, not only to understand the social models that are made, but also designing future scenarios that can fix detected problems and offer new possibilities of life and human relations. The wishes for different models of life present themselves in a variety of locations, ethnic and age groups, but some aspects of contemporary urban life seem to motivate similar searches by changes in social behaviour.

Some authors such as d'Otaviano (2006) show that, in Brazil, in this context, the private condominiums are

growing in number and configurations, dismantling a model that prevailed until the beginning of the 80's, as presented by Caldeira (2000), where the Brazilian cities are organized in a rich Centre and poor suburbs. This new configuration of social conviviality and housing model imply a profound change throughout the city and its traffic flows, security and distribution of classes.

At the same time, the work of scholars like Hill (2007) arose through a perception that has been transforming the market. According to the author, the type of negotiations based only on rationality was outdated and has been replaced by a broader understanding in which subjectivity and emotion are taking a fundamental character in all spheres of consumption.

There are, however, a latent issue for this group of researchers, on how individual perceptions about our society can motivate a prolonged project of experiences, and how such projects are able to give their customers a recognition of subjective values related to urbanization and social conviviality. It is recognized, in the space of the private condominiums, some examples of attempts at generating experiences relating to safety, well-being and even a bucolic rescue of placid life models associated with tranquility of cities in the interior.

This topic of discussion is of particular relevance as it strengthens the association of such experiments with heavily emotional and cultural factors. This is stated because the very act of thinking about housing passes by considerations on family, friendship circles, work and of social coexistence in many different spheres.

By judging an enterprise with a clear attempt to build a life experience in the cited manner, especially by the systemic intervention model present in its project, a residential condominium, located in a neighborhood far from the city centre of Porto Alegre, was defined as object of study of this survey. Again, the idea of observing an experiment that seeks to establish links with such individual and subjective values need a broad observation model, which starts with the understanding of the processes of experience, the expectations of designers and consumers and by the recognition of values in the relation of the expectations with the delivery offered by living in this space.

Part of this interpretive model is based on McLellan (2000) and in the way that the author works with the model of Pine and Gilmore (1999), proposing that the fields of the experience are divided by an axis on which the type of consumer participation defines the effectiveness of experience. In the words of the author, cases of passive participation are not the interest of this research, but rather "activities in which consumers affect the performance or the event itself that triggers the experience".

METHODOLOGY

Through this scope, this research is organized to understand both the model proposed by the designer and the perceptions of the experience of the observed condominium, through in-depth interviews with the orientation of the *laddering* technique. (Reynolds; Gutman. 1988). This model of interview conducted and individual provides means to link attributes of products and services to the consequences in use and, ultimately, these to subjective values that can be both desired at the time of project and perceived at the time of consumption.

The *laddering* technique allows, in addition, a construction of a conceptual map linking such attributes, consequences and values obtained from the interviews. In this way, the methodology of this work consisted in the interview of the designer and residents of the condominium, with the sample defined by saturation. In a later stage, it was built a map for the values wanted in the moment of the

project and a map of the perceptions of the residents (maps attached to this article).

As a way to interpret such data, the values have been grouped into constellations: concept-images that summarize the ideas presented in a cartographic, visual model (Benjamin, 1995). The cycle of experience presented by Pine and Gilmore (1999) is used as a basis to construct these images in which emotional values – both from project and as perceived in experience – are visually divided into quadrants according to conceptual affinity. These cartographic – or constellation like – images make it easier to see the dynamics of experiences lived by the respondents. Finally, it is believed that the comparison between sceneries – projected and from the experience lived in the condominium – can provide subsidies not only to understanding this type of experience, but also contribute to a knowledge base for other similar contexts.

PROPOSING AN EXPERIENCE ROUTE

Understanding a proposal for experience and, likewise, their projection, must pass through an attempt of completeness of the fields of experience as offered by Pine and Gilmore (1999). This logic has the experience in four aspects:

AESTHETIC | ESCAPIST | EDUCATIONAL | ENTERTAINMENT

As mentioned previously, McLellan (2000) establishes the axles to observe the predominance of certain aspects in an experience, through the level of immersion and the type of participation in the experiment:

Figure 1.

A possible model of construction of experience, therefore, within the structured logic between Pine and Gilmore (1999) and McLellan (2000), where the successful experience is one that permeates all areas, should work conducting a consumer, initially in a posture of passive participation, to an active participation. This movement happens when, from the aesthetic impact, the participant is questioning what he should do in that environment. This process finds equivalences with the work of Csikszentmihalyi (1998), if we consider that in this movement can put the participant in a State of enjoyment of the experience.

The case is that the fruition proposed by Csikszentmihalyi (1998) takes place in a more complete state of the experience, in which the consumer is also moving to a state of absorption. The challenge aroused by the escapist attributes of the experience is complemented with a learning process, and when establishing a reward relationship with the proposed challenge, the participant not just touches the educational factors, but becomes to entertain himself by the experience.

This is one of the possible movements between the quadrants of the fields of experience, having the aesthetic issues as principle motivator of the experience. This aesthetic impact is not naturally rationalized, but perceived by a visceral sphere of experience. Norman (2005) shows that, in the cerebral or subjective sphere, the relationship of a participant or customer with the experience is made up of three factors, the visceral, the behavioral and the reflective, and one of them could surpass the others in different moments of the proposed route, or in the evaluation of experience in its entirety.

An essential feature for understanding the model proposed by Norman (2005), is that the visceral and behavioral spheres are not rational, being a rational portion of evaluation of the experience or of the product relegated to the reflective factor. Now, taking this proposition as true, we have a model which advocates subjective factors as more responsible for evaluating and, why not, by the involvement of the individual in a given experience. Having clear this theoretical frame, we begin to observe the motivations

of the designer as values and emotions that were project guidelines in the development of the condominium. The expectation was, according to the proposed method, to identify values, organize them into maps linking them with attributes, preparing the constellations to, finally, understand the dynamics of the projected experience.

THE PROJECT OF THE CONDOMINIUM

The engineer in charge envisioned the possibility of building a differentiated space for housing and convenience, in an area away from the center of Porto Alegre. He idealized the condominium space based on individual concepts and beliefs that became explicit during the interview. He imagined a private condominium, focused on the upper class, which includes a chain of services in its organization, and that coalesced harmonically with the natural ecosystem. Some examples of the implantation denote such concern, as the fact that the geographical space, naturally moist, was not grounded, but drained to waterholes, which not only allowed the construction of the houses without transforming the nature of the ecosystem, as also happened to be an aesthetic differential of the territory.

The space for the construction of houses, divided into 13 residential villages is 170 hectares, with building sites of varying sizes and prices, however, with a model default of individual houses, not allowing semi-detached houses, and whose architecture and territorial distribution provides maximum privacy for the residents.

In the services included in the space planned by the engineer, it is perceived an attempting to a systemic intervention that goes beyond the idea of buying a house, but which seeks to provide these residents amenities at surrounding with suitability to the proposed model. Among these services you can find, for example, an elementary school, an English school, a veterinary center, coffee shop and convenience store, internet access available to the residents, playroom and recreation services, concierge and van to go to other regions of Porto Alegre – with pre-determined schedules – in addition to agreement to mobile ICU service.

One of the big differentiators of the condominium project is that it encompasses a club and a golf course. This direct association with the sport is present, too, as a differential in the condominium project, in order to link the experience of living in this space with values of health and wellness, as can be observed in the conceptual map (annex 1), resulting from the work of laddering done with the designer. Sport and leisure unfold not only at the Golf Club, but also in the practice of football, beach volleyball, tennis, gym, thermal and external swimming pools, plus a lake for non-motorized water sports.

In the depth interview with the entrepreneur, a few points stand out as a guide for the project. The builder claims that the project was made with the family as the focal point, however the map of laddering (annex 1), resulting from the interview, points out a set of values that the engineer sought to include in his project. To make easy the viewing of these values, it was drawn up such values of the laddering and it was prepared the constellation of project, looking for a preview of this set:

Figure 2.

Privacy, well-being, convenience, health, return on investment, reception and security, those were the values identified in the speeches of the engineer. The idea of a project geared toward the family wasn't linked directly to any attributes or consequence, but yes, permeating all design and implementation decisions of the project.

The links of these values with the attributes imagined in the project stage of the condominium clearly establishes, from imagined consequences by the entrepreneur, and will be detailed in a later step.

In a first moment, based on the theoretical model used for the interpretation of the experiment, one can identify the goals of engagement in the experiment proposed by the condominium project. The concepts presented by McLellan (2000), serve as guidance for the distribution of values in the quadrants entertainment, aesthetic, educational, and escapist, from the experience of Pine and Gilmore (1999).

Figure 3.

With respect to the subjectivity of experience, from the conceptual distribution of values in quadrants, there is an intent to produce an experience mostly escapist, with strong disposition to provoke an engagement from a game of recognition of the challenges and rewards that McLellan (2000) identifies as the educational sphere, in condominium living.

The immediate conclusion is that the project seeks to provide an immersive experience via an immediate dependence of active participation of residents. It is always important to note that, in the context of the experiment, the participation and the four quadrants refer to subjective aspects of the participant and his involvement. Therefore, to observe the completeness of experience and consider whether the fruition (Csikszentmihalyi. 1998) establishes itself or not, it should be noted not only what was planned, but mainly what the condominium offers after its implementation, through the eyes of the residents.

VALUES PERCEIVED BY RESIDENTS

The constellation with the values perceived by the residents was organized as follows:

Figure 4.

Identify those values is more complex than in the interview with the designer. The residents do not always have the concept clear to explain the way they live their experiences in the condominium. On the contrary as effective participants of the experience, they have subtle forms of differentiation of the perceived values in the living. This difference is expressed in relation to values assigned by the entrepreneur and even similar concepts presented by different residents and that have different nuances of the same value.

Figure 5.

The values of isolation and privacy are an example of this. As it could be seen in the resulting map of the laddering (annexes 2) done with the six interviewed, the attribute of the houses not being geminated provides a consequence of privacy for the families of residents. All respondents were denoting a feeling of isolation due to the distant location of the condominium, segregating them from the rest of the city and society, or, as they said, the "outside world" to the condominium. Others, however, use the concept of isolation as something positive, reinforcing the idea of respect for privacy and family life. For this same reason, it was decided, in transposition of the graph above, keep "isolation" with the first and

negative sense presented and "privacy" with this second connotation, mainly positive.

An aspect with similar situation are the concepts of "interior life" and "quality of life" that, at first reading, may seem very similar, but have different origins and hence, different meanings in the set of extracted values of the interviews. The residents believe that the condominium provides them a higher quality of life, due to the change in daily lifestyle, provided by numerous factors such as security, the possibility to practice physical activities, a more harmonious coexistence with its neighbors, among others. What, for them, is assigned as a bailout of the interior life model, is precisely the alienation of a large urban centre, and even the geographical factor as predominant in relation to others, in the construction of this value. Despite the recognition of this distance, the interviews do not denote a repudiation of this, on the contrary, this value is directly tied to the set of values sought by all.

Figure 6.

The immersion process, within the theoretical molds previously presented, seems to work with an inclination for an active participation in the experience. This can be viewed in the above graphical representation and in the interviews, in which people show that they collaborate with one another so that the values they perceive in condominium are maintained and, sometimes, expanded. This perception is explicit in moments in which the interviews point to closer relations among residents, and greater respect between them and the service providers of the condominium, explained and summarized in the laddering as a consequence named "citizenship".

The value of the security is pointed to by all as predominant, and it has various links with attributes and consequences provided by the condominium project. Interestingly, this value, quoted sixteen times, is the only one who finds parity with the values quoted by the entrepreneur.

FINDING THE CONTACT BETWEEN PROJECT VALUES AND PERCEIVED VALUES

The interviews and maps obtained from the laddering technique indicate that this equivalence of multiple values that are proposed by the designer and perceived by the participants of the experiment, is closely related to the model of implementation of the security system of the condominium. This is not a proposal for ostentatious security, coupled with the violence, but an implementation linked to the values of coexistence and well-being, also indicated by the interviews.

The security guards are specially trained and make their surveillance without firearms, only through a well-organized communication system. Not to mention the familiarity that security professionals become to have with the residents. Such factors are included in the project stage and were introduced with success, but the factor of the interaction between the actors involved reinforces this idea and begs the host value with great intensity.

In major urban centres the clash of classes is also a generator of insecurity, and the location of the condominium has a surrounding formed by three clusters of misery, in villages and slums. The logic of implementation of the condominium sought to minimize the impact of social contrast of an enterprise of high standard with a surrounding of very low financial income. Peaceful coexistence between these different realities was achieved through actions of training of human resources of the surroundings for the provision of services in the condominium, as well as the creation of an NGO, sustained through compulsory contribution on the condominium monthly fee, which has effective action in these communities. The result is a sense of security by the encouragement to non-violence and for the sake of a harmonic coexistence among different social classes. Education and friendliness of employees and other

service providers collaborate to this positive environment.

It cannot be said, however, that, in the same way that occurred with the security, there was full understanding between the parties at the time of purchase decision. Certainly, many common values were explained in the negotiation, but some respondents cited a fear that the construction of an artificial and controlled space as the condominium would provide them an experience of artificial and controlled life as well. The adjective "false" was used in the interviews and the comparison with the fiction through stories like "1984" and "The Truman Show" has what the buyers thought that could happen from worst in the consolidation of the condominium project. The family and social companionship finds equivalence in the idea of host proposal by the project creator. Some attributes of the condominium were planned to create points of contact between residents, in order to provide this proximity between individuals and families. The first point that attracts the attention in this regard is the spatial organization of the condominium in villages. Is an attempt of rescue of the neighborhoods, where there is greater interaction between neighbours, as formerly happened in urban centres. Moreover, such territorial design minimizes the feeling of having around 5,000 people living together in the same space. Those are values that refer to the idea of interior life perceived by residents. In addition, other project actions, such as building a club and sports and leisure spaces, function as a meeting point for the community, which touches the ideas of companionship, reception, and interior life. Nevertheless, the family is not perceived by residents as a value that permeates all aspects of life in condominium. Different from what was seen in the interview with the entrepreneur, the core value of the appreciation of the family unit, on the part of residents, was less cited than other aspects, such as the companionship and quality of life. What could be realized is that residents shall identify, in condominium, spaces for the development of quality of life and values commonly associated with the traditional family model, while the designer sought to create a space for the development of families. The difference is subtle but striking, since it emerges elderly residents seeking, in the condominium, a

space for a quieter life, as well as professionals who, there, identify the ideal space for work, in models such as the home office, among others.

This is a perception which is essential for the condominium model, since it is designed with an intent and, even so, those who live the experience ends up setting the usage model of that space. This reinforces the idea of an experience having its roots in active participation within the model proposed by Pine and Gilmore (1999). The theoretical support leads to believe that the designer has succeed, in a broad manner, in creating the immersion (Caru; Cova; 2007) and enjoyment (Csikszentmihalyi, 1998) spaces.

More than that, following the logic of the cross between the authors, the residents go through the visceral, behavioral and reflective spheres continuously in condominium living. The case is that the behavioral factor, as proposed by Norman (2005), assumes a prominent space, while the residents and their attitudes contribute to the whole experience rather than the attributes designed by the manufacturer.

The logic of a space for immersion, designed to be used for participants of the experiment with the purest enjoyment, seems a highly productive model for the type of product and service that ends up being a residential condominium. Such perception is directly linked to the fact that the consequences which cause the distinguished values have relationship, mostly, with behavioural changes of residents and service providers, and not so much with the use of attributes or with the aesthetic dimension of the condominium. The attributes, however, fulfil its project role of providing a space for the fruition from the identification of common desires between designer and residents.

Another issue identified as potential of detachment of the residents' perceptions with respect to values that permeated the project is the interference from external factors. It is not up to this research to understand or assign value to these, however, one must cite at least one of them, because it is an attempt of systemic observation, i.e., a search of a vision not just of the product condominium and the experiences there made, but also the wider system that includes what

can interfere, positively or negatively, on the effectiveness of the project.

Because of financial issues between the partners of the project, the implementation of condominium has not occurred within expected. The temporal distance between steps of construction was higher than expected, and its continuity was lead to dispute by one of the parties involved in the project.

Again, it is not the goal, here, to do any judgement of value regarding the parties involved, but the fact is that, due to financial aspects, some services, such as, for example, the uninterrupted transport to other areas of the city, directly depends on the number of homes and residents. Similarly, other services and attributes of the condominium depend on capitalization with sales of land and houses. We must therefore point out that probably some of the perceptions of values can still undergo changes with the evolution of the occupation of spaces available in the condominium. This is not only one of the possibilities seen by the entrepreneur, but also one of the expectations cited by several residents for the future.

CONCLUSIONS

The major contributions of the analysis proposed here reside in the impact that the human factor has on the project. There is a very clear project intentionality of raising emotions, but these are not perceived by physical attributes of the enterprise – buildings, terrain, roads, etc. - but from the relationships that are established between neighbors, families and service providers. On theoretical model of the experience route, we must therefore read projects like this through an approach with the quarters of an active posture of the participant. Similarly, if we think this research as a contribution of project character, it guides the project to be thought in this direction. The great asset of the project is precisely in the design of the relationships between individuals: internal interaction spaces and also to those who live outside of it. It is quite clear, from the results of the interviews, that the manner in which these spaces – now as physical attributes – articulate itself with the services there provided or with the potential user experience – in the company of other people – is that

determines the perception of emotional values of the project.

At the same time, as one realizes that the experience is endowed with strong leadership by participants of the same, it becomes apparent that there is always noise between what was envisioned and what is lived in the experiment. As already pointed out, the project seems to have effectiveness while binds an immersive experience to the posture of individuals, each with respect to others.

The methodological approach also turns out to be configured as a contribution both in theoretical sphere, research, and project support. The laddering technique and organization of values in maps and constellations facilitates the visualization of complex movements of the dynamics of the experience. It is believed that its construction, coupled with the model articulated between Pine and Gilmore (1999) and McLellan (2000) can collaborate with both the reading of complex experiences and its project.

Finally, as an indication of continuity of this research, it can be said that the analysis of territorial space and conviviality give rise to ideas of understanding proceeding from various areas, and is mandatory that they must be observed in future studies. The design of experiences has direct link with the strategic design of accurate systemic vision, and observe this type of enterprise through the product-system models can collaborate greatly to their understanding.

What you can see, after all, is that there is feasibility to produce common desires-based experiences, and that these are not restricted to small controlled spaces. The design for emotion and experience can elevate the logic of the construction of immersion spaces to higher levels, in which man can give vent to their wider and most abstract desires. This idea allows to visualize the design and its capacity for transdisciplinary articulation as an instrument of social change based on common values between citizens of the same urban nucleus.

Figure 7. Laddering Map Designer

Figure 8. Laddering Map residents

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